

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B287
Date: 27 April 2007
Take Off: 15:01:45
Landing: 20:57:36
Flight Time: 5h55m51

Campaign: IASI – METOP and AQUA overpass

Operating Area: Oklahoma ARM site

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Foster	Directflight
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Claire Lee	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Ruth Purvis	FAAM
6	Cloud Physics	Paul James	FAAM
7	AVAPS/CCM2	Doug Anderson	FAAM
8	ARIES	Joss Kent	Met Office
9	MARSS / Wet Neph / PSAP	Dave Pollard	Met Office
10	AMS	Paul Williams	University of Manchester
11	CVI / FWVS	Jeff Brown	Met Office
12	Mission Scientist 2	Alessio Bozzo	University of Bologna
14	Neph	Dave Tiddeman	Met Office
15			
16			
17			
18			
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Flight Track:

B287 Track 27-APR-07

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B287
 Date: 27 APRIL 2007
 Project: IASI METOP and AQUA OVERPASS
 Location: Oklahoma

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
145332		Start-Up	-.12 kft	358	29'36.25N 95'10.06W
145512		ASP	-.12 kft	093	
150145		T/O	-.14 kft	177	
152423	160004	Run 1.1	26.0 kft	320	FL260
153321		Video	26.0 kft	329	UFC1 DFC1
160004	164436	Run 1.2	26.0 kft	336	From D to A
160800		Sonde 1	26.0 kft	348	
161202		Sonde 2	26.0 kft	347	
162000		Sonde 3	26.0 kft	351	
162304		Sonde 4	26.0 kft	351	
162559		Sonde 5	26.0 kft	349	
162800		Sonde 6	26.0 kft	349	
163007		Overpass	26.0 kft	351	MetOp 16:30z
163600		Sonde 7	26.0 kft	353	
164542	164436	Profile 1.1	24.9 - 23.0 kft	352	
165014	170014	Profile 1.2	23.0 - 12.9 kft	177	
170201	171145	Profile 1.3	12.9 - 2.6 kft	357	
171255		Video	2.6 kft	140	UFC2 DFC2
171413	174240	Run 2.1	2.6 kft	187	A to D
174240	174355	Profile 2	2.8 - 3.5 kft	174	
174356	174720	Run 3	3.5 kft	172	3700ft
174721	174754	Profile 3	3.5 - 3.8 kft	169	
174755	174942	Run 4	3.8 kft	171	4000ft
174942	175107	Profile 4	3.8 - 2.9 kft	179	4000ft 3000ft
175205	181121	Run 5	2.7 kft	205	R6 actually R5
181122	181146	Profile 5	2.7 - 2.9 kft	178	R6 actually R5
181318	181827	Run 6	2.9 kft	178	3000ft
182014	183419	Profile 6.1	2.9 - 16.9 kft	013	
183708	185249	Profile 6.2	16.9 - 30.0 kft	353	17000ft
185250	190521	Run 7	30.0 kft	353	
190521	190708	Profile 7	30.0 - 31.0 kft	352	
191156	200838	Run 8	31.0 kft	211	
191458		Sonde 8	31.0 kft	196	
192401		Sonde 9	31.0 kft	195	
192708		Sonde 10	31.0 kft	201	
193001		Sonde 11	31.0 kft	198	
193208		Sonde 12	31.0 kft	196	
193400		Overpass	31.0 kft	190	AQUA 1934Z
194200		Sonde 13	31.0 kft	179	
205736		Land	-.08 kft	173	Ellington airfield
205902		ASP	-.08 kft	177	
210057		End pos	-.08 kft	179	29'36.28N 95'10.06W

B287 Track 27-APR-07

KEFD -> KHOU - Overview

NavData Cycle 2007-4 Expires: Thursday, 10 May 2007.

Scale: 1:4182512 (1 inch = 57.36 naut mi). Printed on 26 Apr 2007

JEPPESEN

FliteStar 9.2.0.2

Sortie Brief – Oklahoma

Flight B287

Fri 27th April 2007

Mission Scientist: Clare Lee

Briefing: 0800L 1300Z

Take off: 1000L 1500Z

Land: 1530L 2030Z

Satellite overpass = 16:30Z (MetOp) & 19:34Z (AQUA)

Aim: To underfly IASI on the Metop satellite and AIRS on AQUA in the vicinity of the ARM site coordinated with the overpasses.

Location: Over ARM instrument site located near Lamont, Oklahoma.

Weather conditions: Clear skies or Broken cloud.

Key instruments: ARIES, MARSS, SWS, AVAPS, Core Chem, Cloud Phys

Fixed Points: BAe 146 to follow fixed ground positions as follows:

Over OKLAHOMA

Fixed point A: (37°20' N, 97°35' W)

Fixed point B: (35°50' N, 97° 36' W)

Fixed point C: (34°20' N, 97°37' W)

Fixed point D: (33°30' N, 97°35' W)

1. Take off from Houston and transit to Oklahoma point D to arrive at FL260 (60 mins)
2. SLR from D to A at FL260 (45 mins) overpass 1 occurs during this run
3. Stepped profile descent from A to finish at A at 2700ft (30 mins)
4. SLR from A to D at 2700ft (65 mins)
5. Profile ascent from D to A to FL300 (50 mins)
6. SLR from A to D at FL300 (45 mins) overpass 2 occurs during this run
7. Transit direct to Houston (40 mins)

Drop sonde pattern: aim is to launch sondes with good coverage along the sub-satellite track with particular density at the overpass time.

Satellite overpass – 1630Z

Dropsonde launch:	Time Z	Time relative to overpass (mins)
#1	1608	T-22
#2	1612	T-18
#3	1620	T-10
#4	1623	T-7
#5	1626	T-4
#6	1628	T-2
#7	1636	T+6
#8	1642	T+12

Satellite overpass – 1934Z

Dropsonde launch:	Time Z	Time relative to overpass (mins)
#1	1914	T-20
#2	1924	T-10
#3	1927	T-7
#4	1930	T-4
#5	1932	T-2
#6	1942	T+8

ARIES operations

During low level run, mainly NADIR with short ZEN view (under clear parts)

During high level runs NADIR with short Zenith near end of run

Mission Scientists De-brief
Flight B287 Oklaholma ARM-CART site
Friday 27th April 2007

Mission scientist: Clare Lee

Aims

The aim of the sortie was to fly near the sub-satellite track of both MetOp and AQUA and in conjunction with the ARM site, with WB57, in partially cloudy skies. The run was extended compared to previous flights to attain clear slots and still pass the ARM site.

Weather conditions

Broken shallow Cu (tops 8kft) at either end of the run, increasing to StCu with a large convective thunderstorm over Oklahoma City at the centre of the runs (tops FL300 – 400). Note around the edges of the deep convection increases in NO_x and CO were observed, probably due to the down flow of air. Some cirrus was observed overhead at the start of the sortie, but there were clear skies above the low cloud during second half.

Sortie

This flight was successful for a more complicated cloud case, with Cu or StCu coverage for most of the sortie.

A transit was made towards the Southerly point (D) with an immediate run at FL260. At point D a run at FL260 was made towards A (northern point). 7 drop sondes were launched at equal spaces along the track, 4 of which were spaced so that at the time of the overpass they were at different altitudes in the atmosphere. An interrupted profile descent was made down to 2700ft, followed by a straight and level run from A towards D at 2700ft. To avoid Oklahoma City, a profile to 3700ft and short run was made. Altitude was increased to 4000ft due to air traffic. At the Southern side of the city a descent was eventually made to 2800ft to continue the run to point D. This run was flown at 2800ft, but interrupted due to air traffic, and was continued at 3000ft. A profile was made to FL300, although interrupted due to air traffic, and occasionally off track to avoid the large convective centres. A short run at FL300 was flown to point A. The reciprocal run was made at FL310. During this run South, 6 drop sondes were launched, separated appropriately for the AQUA overpass. Note due to the large storm over Oklahoma City some of the run went off track to avoid it. Fuel was low towards the end of the run and hence the track was shifted slightly ready for transit to Ellington.

During the transit back increases were seen on the AMS and core chem, which maybe from the Houston pollution plume.

Instrument Status

SWS- 1 min zenith data lost
MARSS – OK, except of ch 16

SEADAS – crashed during flight, but worked again OK. There will be 2 separate files to analyse

AVAPS – probs with 1st sonde GPS

TWC – some problems at the beginning of the flight

SATCOM – no messages observed from aircraft

SID2 – failed between approx 1925Z and 1955, SID 1 OK

WB-57 status

Unfortunately the NAST-M was not working.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.287** Date **27/04/07** Name **C. LEE** Page **1** of **9**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
~1500Z 150145					T10 Houston, Ellington ~ 7/8 Ci above.
1512		FL180			Moist layer as ascending up ~ 7kft. In cloud T-20 ice particles.
1517					Can see dew slot ahead (to N) as expected on sat. pic.
		FL260	321	30°48'N 95°42'W	Small turbulence. Small turbulence Small turbulence . T = -28.8°C, T _D = -31.54°C
1522Z 152423	R1	FL260	320	31°06'N 95°54'W	Run 1. Started early as at altitude. In clear sky. Ci above ~ 6/8, 4/8 StW. from Leonia → pt. D.
1531					7/8 StW below, ~ 2/2 Ci requested ANICS to do zenith occasionally during transit part.
153744					Clear air turbulence (small level)
1539				32°12'N 96°24'W	Slowly turning towards D.
1540					V. v. small turbulence only now.
1543					4/8 W to N, haze to S. 6/8 Ci v. thin above.
1547					Clear above ahead, 5/8 W below.
1548					Going into dry slot.
1550			312	32°48'N 97°06'W	Definitely clear above. 4/8 W below prob. ~ 8kft.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.287** Date **27/04/07** Name **C. LEE** Page **2** of **9**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1557					W starting to build to N. clear above.
160004	R1.2	FL260	348	33° 30' N 97° 30' W	Run D → A. Clear above. W 618 now extending up to FL260 or FL300 ahead, over slight gap at moment.
1607					turbulence as a <u>approaching convection</u> . over low level stuff ~ 818 W.
160800	D1	FL260	348	34° 12' N 97° 36' W	Dropsonde release. T = -35°, T _D = -40 Wind: 28 ms ⁻¹ / 281° NO GPS values coming back from sonde.
1611					Large variation in W, currently over gap. Some going to to low 1000ft. high, to massive ones > FL300
161202	D2	FL260	351	34° 30' N 97° 36' W	Dropsonde 2. GPS OK. Wind 24 ms ⁻¹ / 266° T = -34.6, T _D = -41.8°
161804					Sonde 1 on ground.
162000	D3	FL260	351	35° 12' N 97° 36' W	Dropsonde 3. GPS OK. Wind 26 ms ⁻¹ / 285°, T = -34, T _D = -44
162110					In cloud ^{ledge} , tops ~ FL300 ~ 800 max ice crystals. Associated turbulence.
162146					Sonde 2 on ground.
162304	D4	FL260	352	35° 30' N 97° 36' W	Dropsonde 4

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.287** Date 27/04/07 Name C. LEE Page 3 of 9

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					Wind 24ms ⁻¹ / 277°, T = -34.93°C GPS winds at 24kft. T _D = -34.69°C
					Still in cloud.
162559	D5	F2260	350	97°36'W / 35°48'N	Dropsonde 5. Some intermittent probs with D5. wind 26ms ⁻¹ / 260° Still in cloud.
162800	D6	F2260	350	35°54'N / 97°36'W	Dropsonde 6. GPS winds. wind 27ms ⁻¹ / 269°
1629					Out of cloud.
1630					Metop over pass. low level STW ~ 5kft tops 4/8 clear above.
163040					Sonde 3 land.
163128					Sonde 4 land.
1632					Patch 60 ahead ~ 3/8
1633					Sonde 5 land.
1634					O ₃ 130ppb peaked ~ 50ppb above background.
					All W to N very low level not seeing cells as seen around pt. B.
163600	D7	F2260	353	38°36'N / 97°36'W	Dropsonde 7. GPS OK. Wind 20ms ⁻¹ / 287°
163758					Sonde 6 landed. clear above. 2/8 W low level.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B**.....287 Date 27/04/07 Name C. LEE Page 4 of 9

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
164220					ARIES + SWS zenith seeing clear sky.
1643					MARSS, ARIES + SWS starting to see structure overhead. Ci threatening ahead. clear below.
164436	PI. 2 _{end}	FL260	353		End run. Still heading N to ensure sockle signal.
164436	PI ↓	FL260	353	37°18'N 97°30'W	Descent profile
1645					Sockle 7 landed.
164736	PI int.	FL230	354		Profile intercept. turning for reciprocal heading. 7/8 Ci overhead. 2/8 W below.
165014	PI rec.	FL230	177		Recommence profile heading towards D.
1653					In clear slot above + below. Ahead 7/8 W, 4/8 Ci low level.
1658		FL170			Over 4/8 W, 5/8 Ci above.
17004	PI int.	FL130	190	36°42'N 97°30'W Near ARM site bt.	Intercept profile for reciprocal to A.
					8/8 SW below, 1/8 Ci overhead.
170201	PI ³ rec. ↓	FL130	355		Heading towards A + clearer slot again.
1707		8000ft.	355		Passing tops of W. Very patchy near pt. A.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.287** Date **27/04/07** Name **C LEE** Page **5** of **9**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
171145	P1.3	2700ft.	350	37°18'N 97°36'W	Profile end. at pt-A Turning right for low level on C/S W, C/S G ahead.
171413	R2.1	2700ft.	187	37°18'N 97°30'W	Run from A → D.
172130					6/8 StW above
1730					~3/8 W. Thick patch moved S.
1738					Cloud thickening above. 7/8 StW.
1741			182	35°42'N 97°30'W	Precipitation on windscreen. large storm to right. with lightning
174240	R2.lead	2700ft.	178		End run to go over Oklahoma City
174240	P2↑	2700ft.			
174355	P2.lead	3700ft.	172		
174355	R3	3700ft.	172	35°30'N 97°30'W	Running B → C over Oklahoma City thick clouds above + precip large lightning storm to right. Running slightly off line to get past storms + city.
174720	R3.lead	3700ft.	171		End run + profile up at request of air traffic.
174720	P3↑	4000ft.			
174754	R4	4000ft.	171		Restarting run to South. edging right to get back on track.
					Winds 4ms ⁻¹ / 203°
1749					T = 13.5°, T _D = 4.7°C.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.287** Date **2.7.10.07** Name **C. LEE** Page **6** of **9**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
174942	R4end	4000ft.			Descending at other side of
174942	P4↓	4000ft.	201		Oklahehoma.
175134	P4end	3000ft.			End profile. Can't go lower due to air traffic
175107	R5	3000ft.	210		Just got clearance to 2700ft.
	P5↓	3000ft.			After few seconds into Run.
	P5end	2800ft.	203		
					Out of rain in the last 2 mins.
					Big SW above not too thick.
175205	R5	2800ft.	187.		Continuing on S towards pt. D.
1758					Lots of variation in SW
					above - seen in MASS
1800					NOx, CO rising, + AMS
1801					W thinning + more patchy as
					leading S towards D.
1806		2800ft.		34920N / 97231W	Precip from isolated cell.
					for ~ 30 secs.
1810					Clear above. ARIES doing really.
181121	R5end	2800ft.			Air traffic making us to go up.
181122	P5↑	3800ft.			
181146	R5end	3000ft.			
181318	R6	3000ft.	178		Still leading South
					Patchy W overhead.
181827	R6end	3000ft.			At pt. D end run, turning right.
182014	P6↑	3000ft.	013	38701N / 97381W	Precip patchy, leading N to A.
					Broken W. ~ 418

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B**.....**287** Date **27/04/07** Name **C. LEE** Page **7** of **9**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					Shallow Cu ahead.
1827		9200ft.	352		Cloud base.
1828		9600ft.			In cloud. + out quickly.
1830		11500ft.			Out of cloud. In cloud. + out quickly. Tops varying - larger to N. as climbing to N, tops increasing at similar rate.
1832		14800ft.			In cloud. ice particles.
1833		15300ft.			Out of cloud.
183350		16600ft.			Near local cloud tops. Higher ahead.
183419	P6 ^{int} int	17000ft.			Interupt. profile due to air traffic. In cloud.
1835			355		In + out of tops.
183708	P6 ^{rec}	17000ft.	356	34°22' N / 97°30' W ↙	Profile recommenced after permission between pt. C + Oklahoma city Climbing thro' cloud - turbulent - Heading into Oklahoma City storm.
1840					SEADPs comp. crashed. - may have lost 2D data.
1847		26400			Still climbing thro' cloud. N-B. have moved slightly off + on track to avoid very convective cells.
1849		27480			Out of cloud. ~ pt. B. Clear above. 6/8 W below.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.287** Date 27/04/07 Name C. LEE Page 8 of 9

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
185249	P6 ² _{end}				
185250	R7	FL300	353		Run at high level heading N.
190521	R7 _{end}	FL300			Clear above. End run near pt. A
190521	P7 [↑]	FL300			Profiling up slightly up.
190708	P7 _{end}	FL310		37°24'N / 97°36'W	procedural turn to left. at pt. A. SEMPAS working again. Starting new file for after crash. - will have to analyse separately.
1909					Clear above, 6/8 W below.
191156	R8	FL310	212	37°18'N / 97°30'W	Run A → D clear above, 9/8 W below. shallow
191458	D8	FL310	193	37°0'N / 97°30'W	Sonde drop 8
1922					Large storm ahead over Oklahoma City ^{+pt. B} - bearing left ^{right} slightly to avoid Can't go over ^(FL400) + not enough fuel to sharpen it.
192401	D9	FL310			Sonde release 9 GPS ON. winds 25ms ⁻¹ / 243°
1926					Sonde 8 on ground. All insts. showing clear above.
192708	D10	FL310	201	36°0'N / 97°42'W	Sonde release 10. GPS ON. wind 23ms ⁻¹ / 254°
193001	D11	FL310	198	35°48'N / 97°42'W	Dropsonde release 10. GPS ON winds 21ms ⁻¹ / 253°
193208	D12	FL310	195	35°	Dropsonde release 11 winds 21ms ⁻¹ / 254°

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.287** Date **27/04/07** Name **C. LEE** Page **9** of **9**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1934 Z					Send altitudes for 9,10,11,12: 1068, 3008, 5421, 7391m
193641					Off max dist. from track, coming around huge storm to get back on track.
1935			181.		Send 9 on ground.
1925					SID 2 died. → SID 1 OK.
⊕					Still clear above. No Ci
1939					Some turbulence - close vicinity to W storm.
1940					Send 10 on ground Send 11 lost signal on ground? Coming back on track.
1941					O ₃ high (200ppb). - close to storm
194200	D13	FL310	179		Send 13 release. GPS OK. winds 31ms ⁻¹ / 268° ^{slightly} intermittent.
					Clear sky above. → 4/8 W below only shallow.
					Low on fuel so drifting towards Ellington rather than following exact track.
					T = -42.9, T _D = -57.5°C
1953					Send 3 landed.
1955 200838	RS end	FL310			SID 2 working again. Land at Ellington (Houston)

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B287 **T/O:** 150145
Date of flight: 27 APRIL 2007 **Land:** 205736

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt	no	hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:B287_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>	yes	<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful.</p> <p>X =a</p> <p>Start = 150100 End = 205800</p> <p>Time data processed to = 161933 2dproc files present? *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat yes</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE</p> <p>i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D'</p> <p>ii). exit</p>	yes	<p>Use PVWAVE for this section</p> <p>Error message about HDDR file should be ignored. Records =31</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>	yes	<p>Mfda - mfdb</p>
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>	<p>No nevz broken</p>	<p>Correlated?</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B287 **T/O:** 150145
Date of flight: 27 APRIL 2007 **Land:** 205736

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	Yes	
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. 1.8ccs⁻¹</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Min size =2 Vol flow rate = 0.8
3) FLOODS> WAVE i). WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' ii). WAVE> exit	Yes	Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		File not found
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and NEPH peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph total blue scatter</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>		Merged OK?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B287a **T/O:** 150145
Date of flight: 27 APRIL 2007 **Land:** 205736

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt	no	hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B287a **T/O:** 150145
Date of flight: 27 APRIL 2007 **Land:** 205736

B) 2D PROCESSING		REPROCESS +1hr
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	yes	
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)	yes	
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	yes	
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) Unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B282.zip	yes	Size of Bnnn.dat = 665093
6) FLOODS> WAVE WAVE> CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B287.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B287_seadas.dat WAVE> exit	yes	Use PVWAVE for this section Blocks read = 84796 Blocks written = 84796 Bad reads =0
7) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] B287_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 5 min)</i> f) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land + 5 min)</i> g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data: Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N	yes	Start = 150100 End = 205800 Ignore error message scroll (vestigial error from tapes) FRW, FSP, IMB, PCA,SEC f in PMSDATA? Are they non-zero in size? yes
8) FLOODS> WAVE i). WAVE> imagedisplay a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Time from IWC plot: N d) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP e) Start time: <i>As in 7e above</i> f) End time: <i>As in 7f above</i> g) Time interval (sec): 5 recommended (0 for all images) ii). WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 1 min)</i> e) Enter end time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 1 min)</i> f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks: 10 iii). WAVE> exit to create files iv). FTP ascii *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC v). Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter vi). Output as pdf file (720 dpi resolution), appending name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files	yes	2D image display and printing Must be done from FLOODS itself. 2DC – noise , angular small ice & dendrites max 800um 2DP – Doesn't appear to be any images, all ice seen at 240mb. Prepare imagery for Core data From own PC again Start = 150100 End = 205800 FAAM_YYYYMMDD_RO_ Bnnn_2Dx-images.ps Notes on this in instructions

<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:B287_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>		<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful.</p> <p>X =a</p> <p>Start = 150100 End = 205800</p> <p>Time data processed to = 161933 2dproc files present? *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat yes</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit</p>		<p>Use PVWAVE for this section</p> <p>Error message about HDDR file should be ignored. Records =31</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>		<p>Mfda - mfdb</p>
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>	<p>No nevz broken</p>	<p>Correlated?</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B287a **T/O:** 150145
Date of flight: 27 APRIL 2007 **Land:** 205736

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:		
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. 1.8ccs⁻¹</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Min size =2 Vol flow rate = 0.8
3) FLOODS> WAVE i). WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' ii). WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Mfdb - mfdc
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and NEPH peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph total blue scatter</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>		Merged OK?

FAAM Dropsonde Flight Log

Flight No.	B287	Date	27 Apr 2007
Page No.	1 of 2	Operator	Doug Anderson

GMT	Sonde No.	Event	Comments
		<i>e.g. launch, land</i>	<i>e.g. wind data? PTH data? Lat/Long NB strings of dropsonde data contain: time, pressure hPa, T deg C, RH %, wind direction deg, wind speed m/s, longitude, latitude, height m</i>
			Sondes 1-7 (page 1) launched around the 1630Z MetOp satellite overpass
16:08:03	1	Launch	359.70 -34.90 52.61 280.20 29.10 -16.80 -97.611700 34.202400 7927.40
16:18:45	1	land	984.00 23.01 71.13 282.83 0.01 -0.01 -97.523170 34.208306 60.03 Launched at Overpass T-22. GPS data before launch but none for whole drop.
16:12:18	2	Launch	359.50 -34.20 56.83 276.90 25.40 -18.30 -97.611800 34.564700 7932.20
16:21:17	2	land	978.93 16.63 74.56 130.77 5.74 -11.33 -97.523734 34.554510 107.96 Launched at Overpass T-18. GPS good from almost right after launch
16:20:03	3	Launch	359.20 -35.10 40.24 287.20 27.50 -15.50 -97.606500 35.221200 7937.20
16:30:03	3	land	976.03 16.62 62.48 174.92 1.64 -0.29 -97.504381 35.228892 149.72 Launched at Overpass T-7.
16:27:00	4	Launch	359.90 -35.30 105.08 263.50 24.50 -16.90 -97.600000 35.823000 7923.50
16:30:02	4	land	972.91 14.43 83.71 118.72 118.77 -0.08 -98.238532 35.734279 99999.00 Launched at Overpass T-4.
16:28:03	5	Launch	359.30 -35.70 103.03 268.60 28.30 -16.70 -97.599100 35.914800 7935.20
16:37:42	5	land	980.88 13.02 80.95 193.56 6.22 -10.95 -97.473206 35.909442 106.39 Launched at Overpass T-2.
16:30:36	6	Launch	359.20 -36.00 51.69 268.40 24.80 -14.90 -97.596500 36.144200 7936.90
16:32:36	6	land	982.10 13.08 93.23 155.97 2.54 -7.69 -97.527354 35.739946 146.80
16:36:03	7	Launch	359.70 -35.10 22.87 285.60 22.60 -16.20 -97.590900 36.626400 7928.30
16:45:32	7	land	981.21 16.50 63.02 251.13 7.09 -0.89 -97.471748 36.614670 141.10

Flight No.	B287	Date	27 Apr 2007
Page No.	2 of 2	Operator	Doug Anderson

GMT	Sonde No.	Event	Comments
		<i>e.g. launch, land</i>	<i>e.g. wind data? PTH data? Lat/Long NB strings of dropsonde data contain: time, pressure hPa, T deg C, RH %, wind direction deg, wind speed m/s, longitude, latitude, height m</i>
			Sondes 8-12 (page 2) launched around the 1934Z AQUA satellite overpass
19:15:00	8	Launch	286.70 -48.10 39.54 264.10 27.20 -15.50 -97.576300 37.145800 9465.10
19:25:31	8	land	@19:25:25 : 969.86 19.98 51.72 300.86 7.43 -2.29 -97.423666 37.113123 Poor GPS from roughly half way through drop
19:24:03	9	Launch	287.20 -48.30 52.15 246.20 25.30 -15.60 -97.627600 36.306100 9454.70
19:35:15	9	land	974.49 19.05 58.94 244.14 11.81 -0.19 -97.480266 36.288565 170.76 Weak telemetry at lower levels
19:27:12	10	Launch	287.40 -48.20 75.15 250.10 24.10 -16.10 -97.704800 36.036400 9450.10
19:38:13	10	land	@19:38:06 : 970.83 17.73 57.49 203.82 8.16 -7.20 -97.567449 36.024460 198.86
19:30:03	11	Launch	287.20 -48.00 70.15 254.30 21.50 -16.30 -97.778900 35.795400 9455.00
19:41:03	11	land	@19:40:58 : 971.07 15.73 70.95 202.41 8.39 -8.41 -97.646958 35.785172 187.05
19:32:12	12	Launch	287.30 -47.80 54.87 255.30 21.30 -16.20 -97.824900 35.610600 9452.70
19:43:14	12	land	974.59 14.27 79.56 227.79 3.05 -0.11 -97.699021 35.602417 154.41
19:42:03	13	Launch	286.90 -45.20 22.94 268.30 31.20 -15.80 -97.711200 34.720100 9461.00
19:52:59	13	land	977.14 18.59 71.42 106.88 4.74 -11.84 -97.591352 34.722963 101.15
	14	Launch	
	14	land	
		Launch	
		land	

B287 CVI log

4/27/07 3:23:20 PM zero at 26KFT
4/27/07 3:43:06 PM zero at 26KFT
4/27/07 4:00:29 PM zero at 26KFT point d
4/27/07 4:16:48 PM zero at 26KFT
4/27/07 4:24:00 PM zero at 26KFT
4/27/07 4:30:03 PM zero at 26KFT
4/27/07 4:35:40 PM zero at 26KFT
4/27/07 4:48:36 PM zero at 23KFT
4/27/07 5:00:43 PM zero at 13KFT
4/27/07 6:24:22 PM zero during profile
4/27/07 7:06:09 PM zero 30kft
4/27/07 7:13:25 PM zero 30kft
4/27/07 7:13:57 PM oops finally stopped zero 30kft
4/27/07 7:20:44 PM zero 30kft
4/27/07 7:26:35 PM zero 30kft
4/27/07 7:32:19 PM zero 30kft
4/27/07 7:39:05 PM zero 30kft

B287_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

```

13:20:12.47 --- - - - -
13:20:12.47 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
13:20:12.47 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
                               tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
13:20:12.47 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B287
13:20:12.47 --- - - - -
13:20:40.85 SWS - - - - Initialising: VIS OK NIR OK
13:20:49.62 USH - - - - Initialising: VIS OK NIR OK
13:20:55.82 LSH - - - - Initialising: VIS OK NIR OK
13:21:05.63 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
13:21:11.47 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
13:21:16.79 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
13:21:30.25 SWS - - 500 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 500ms.
13:21:35.47 SWS - - - 500 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 500ms.
13:21:41.58 USH - - 350 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 350ms.
13:21:46.83 USH - - - 350 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 350ms.
13:21:52.34 LSH - - 990 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 990ms.
13:21:56.21 LSH - - - 990 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 990ms.
13:21:58.32 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:21:58.32 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:21:58.34 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:22:02.87 USH - - - - Idling
13:22:04.75 SWS - - - - Idling
13:22:09.17 LSH - - - - Idling
13:22:42.28 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:22:42.28 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:22:42.28 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:25:27.45 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:25:27.52 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:25:27.69 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:25:31.83 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:25:33.13 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:25:37.83 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:26:04.87 SWS - - 350 - VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 350ms.
13:26:08.90 SWS - - 200 - VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 200ms.
13:26:14.59 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:26:14.61 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:26:14.65 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:26:18.73 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:26:20.44 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:26:24.93 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:26:36.58 --- - - - - *** sws to aft for
13:26:54.74 --- - - - - *** sws to aft for t/o
14:41:08.33 USH - - 400 - VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 400ms.
14:41:13.79 USH - - 300 - VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 300ms.
14:41:24.75 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
14:41:32.51 SWS - - - - Idling
14:41:34.35 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:41:36.66 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:41:42.08 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:41:48.36 SWS - - 400 NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
14:42:14.11 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
14:42:24.58 SWS - - - - Idling
14:42:30.28 SWS - - - - Instrument closed.
14:43:19.60 SWS - - - - Initialising: VIS OK NIR OK
14:43:35.06 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
14:43:49.37 USH - - 250 - VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
14:43:53.18 SWS - - 75  NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 75ms.
14:44:00.42 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:44:00.50 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:44:00.79 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:44:03.37 SWS - - - - Idling
14:44:04.87 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:44:11.27 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:44:18.32 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:44:46.51 --- - - - - *** Lost NIR trace on SWS head

```

14:45:13.41	---	-	-	-	*** Restored after re-initialising and resetting a few times - monitor
15:07:16.57	SWS	174R	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
15:07:25.51	SWS	-	-	400	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 400ms.
15:07:29.71	SWS	-	-	-	350 NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 350ms.
15:07:39.19	SWS	-	-	-	500 NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 500ms.
15:07:52.66	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:07:52.67	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:07:52.74	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:07:56.59	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:07:58.30	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:08:03.39	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:11:18.71	SWS	-	-	750	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
15:11:22.88	SWS	-	-	-	750 NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
15:11:26.32	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:11:34.26	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:14:42.28	USH	-	-	200	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 200ms.
15:14:46.17	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:14:46.24	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:14:46.84	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:14:50.30	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:14:54.12	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:14:57.18	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:20:46.30	SWS	-	-	500	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
15:20:49.43	SWS	-	-	-	500 NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
15:20:53.87	USH	-	-	100	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
15:20:58.01	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:20:58.03	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:20:58.09	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:21:01.95	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:21:03.86	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:21:08.55	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:21:56.43	USH	-	-	200	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
15:22:02.36	USH	-	-	-	750 NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 750ms.
15:22:11.23	USH	-	-	150	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
15:22:15.33	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:22:15.38	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:22:15.61	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:22:20.77	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:22:23.48	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:22:26.08	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:24:11.00	USH	-	-	-	500 NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
15:24:14.82	USH	-	-	100	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
15:24:20.40	SWS	-	-	400	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
15:24:46.70	---	-	-	-	*** start of run 1.1 152423
15:24:49.04	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:24:49.07	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:24:49.14	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:24:49.97	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:24:54.48	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:24:55.42	USH	-	-	-	Idling
15:24:59.78	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:25:12.15	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:25:17.59	USH	-	-	-	Idling
15:25:19.86	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:27:15.99	---	-	-	-	*** between 2/8 ac3 and 5/8 cil
15:27:29.37	LSH	-	-	500	VIS int.time changed from 990ms to 500ms.
15:27:39.91	SWS	-	-	300	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 300ms.
15:27:43.90	LSH	-	-	350	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 350ms.
15:27:47.23	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:27:47.23	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:27:47.64	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:27:52.65	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:27:52.87	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:27:57.98	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:28:15.20	SWS	-	-	200	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
15:28:19.09	SWS	-	-	-	350 NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 350ms.
15:28:23.48	SWS	-	-	100	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
15:28:26.68	SWS	-	-	-	250 NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 250ms.

15:28:33.38	LSH	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 250ms.
15:28:40.38	LSH	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 150ms.
15:28:43.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:28:43.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:28:43.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:28:46.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:28:48.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:28:53.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:29:22.75	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
15:29:24.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:29:27.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:31:38.81	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud below now 7/8 ac3
15:36:31.51	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
15:36:42.92	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 250ms to 200ms.
15:36:46.24	SWS	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 350ms.
15:36:49.77	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 400ms.
15:36:52.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:36:52.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:36:52.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:36:56.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:36:58.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:36:59.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:37:03.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:37:08.19	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
15:37:15.77	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
15:37:21.78	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
15:37:27.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:37:31.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
15:37:40.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Initialising: VIS OK NIR OK
15:37:44.72	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 500ms.
15:37:50.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:38:00.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:38:02.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:38:07.64	SWS	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 500ms.
15:38:14.22	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
15:38:21.06	SWS	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 500ms.
15:38:22.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:38:30.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:39:24.95	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
15:39:33.40	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
15:39:36.39	SWS	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 400ms.
15:39:41.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:39:41.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:39:41.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:39:46.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:39:47.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:39:51.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:43:29.25	---	-	-	-	-	*** back to 2/8 ac3 below
15:43:31.39	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
15:43:37.72	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 300ms.
15:43:43.31	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
15:43:46.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:43:46.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:43:46.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:43:52.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:43:55.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:43:57.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:43:58.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:43:58.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:43:58.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:44:04.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:44:06.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:44:09.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:46:14.00	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
15:46:23.76	SWS	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 400ms.
15:46:26.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:46:26.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:46:27.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:46:31.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

15:46:32.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:46:37.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:47:39.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:47:39.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:47:39.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:47:43.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:47:45.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:47:50.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:47:53.73	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
15:47:56.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:48:07.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:48:12.45	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
15:48:16.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:48:20.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:48:36.39	LSH	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 350ms.
15:48:38.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:48:49.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:48:56.20	LSH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 300ms.
15:48:59.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:48:59.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:48:59.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:49:04.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:49:04.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:49:10.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:49:19.39	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 100ms.
15:49:22.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:49:27.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:49:29.13	LSH	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
15:49:31.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:49:41.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:50:22.47	---	-	-	-	-	*** having difficulty keeping up with ac3 below
15:53:13.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:53:14.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:53:14.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:53:18.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:53:19.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:53:24.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:54:15.20	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
15:54:20.07	SWS	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 350ms.
15:54:24.08	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 400ms.
15:54:26.98	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
15:54:31.09	SWS	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 500ms.
15:54:34.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:54:42.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:54:57.85	LSH	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 350ms.
15:55:02.50	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 500ms.
15:55:06.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:17.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:55:27.29	SWS	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
15:55:32.76	SWS	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
15:55:34.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:42.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:55:47.37	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
15:55:50.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:56:02.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:56:03.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:56:48.14	LSH	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 350ms.
15:56:51.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:57:01.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:57:05.31	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
15:57:09.62	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 150ms.
15:57:16.97	SWS	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 300ms.
15:57:21.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:57:21.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:57:21.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:57:24.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:57:26.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:57:32.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

15:59:16.40	---	-	-	-	*** ac cast below 3/8 less than 1/8 cil above
15:59:38.91	SWS	-	-	300	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 300ms.
15:59:44.83	SWS	-	-	-	400 NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 400ms.
15:59:48.77	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:59:53.21	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:00:52.72	---	-	-	-	*** start of run 1.2 160004
16:01:08.31	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:01:08.77	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:01:09.27	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:01:13.21	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:01:13.77	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:01:19.60	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:05:13.98	SWS	-	-	200	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
16:05:15.91	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:05:20.35	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:05:31.25	SWS	-	-	100	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
16:05:35.92	SWS	-	-	-	300 NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 300ms.
16:05:38.82	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:05:42.26	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:07:04.95	LSH	-	-	300	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 300ms.
16:07:11.20	LSH	-	-	200	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
16:07:15.05	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:07:15.10	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:07:15.96	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:07:18.55	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:07:20.73	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:07:26.33	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:07:58.72	---	-	-	-	*** now over 7/8 ac8 (cast)
16:08:14.48	SWS	-	-	75	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
16:08:19.44	SWS	-	-	50	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 50ms.
16:08:22.04	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:08:25.48	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:08:26.96	LSH	-	-	150	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
16:08:31.63	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:08:41.97	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:10:32.36	SWS	6F	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
16:10:40.37	SWS	-	-	200	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 200ms.
16:10:43.88	SWS	-	-	400	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 400ms.
16:10:47.49	SWS	-	-	-	750 NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 750ms.
16:10:53.21	LSH	-	-	75	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 75ms.
16:10:56.45	LSH	-	-	-	400 NIR int.time changed from 990ms to 400ms.
16:10:58.33	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:10:58.35	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:10:58.36	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:11:02.97	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:11:04.17	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:11:06.27	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:12:57.98	LSH	-	-	200	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 200ms.
16:16:54.32	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:16:54.47	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:16:54.75	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:16:58.96	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:17:00.19	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:17:02.27	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:17:18.99	SWS	-	-	300	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 300ms.
16:17:22.92	SWS	-	-	-	300 NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 300ms.
16:17:24.50	SWS	174R	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
16:17:29.09	SWS	-	-	200	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
16:17:35.07	SWS	-	-	100	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
16:17:44.15	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:17:47.60	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:17:49.09	LSH	-	-	150	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
16:17:58.67	LSH	-	-	-	750 NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
16:18:10.21	SWS	-	-	75	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
16:18:13.17	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:18:13.17	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:18:13.22	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:18:16.62	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:18:18.81	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

16:18:21.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:18:49.03	LSH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
16:19:23.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** currently amongst 4/8 cb
16:20:18.82	LSH	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
16:20:24.91	SWS	-	-	-	15	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 15ms.
16:20:28.81	SWS	-	-	-	75	NIR int.time changed from 15ms to 75ms.
16:20:31.94	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 50ms.
16:20:35.96	SWS	-	-	15	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 15ms.
16:20:43.70	LSH	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
16:20:45.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:20:46.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:20:46.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:20:47.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:20:51.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:20:51.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:21:54.49	---	-	-	-	-	*** in cloud (anvil?)
16:22:04.46	LSH	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 50ms.
16:22:07.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:22:12.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:24:25.49	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 15ms to 100ms.
16:24:31.00	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
16:24:34.80	SWS	-	-	15	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 15ms.
16:24:37.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:24:38.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:24:41.20	SWS	-	-	-	150	NIR int.time changed from 75ms to 150ms.
16:24:44.67	SWS	-	-	-	350	NIR int.time changed from 150ms to 350ms.
16:24:48.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:24:52.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:24:55.28	USH	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 150ms.
16:24:59.22	USH	-	-	-	990	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 990ms.
16:25:04.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:25:07.23	LSH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 200ms.
16:25:11.76	LSH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
16:25:14.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:25:16.13	LSH	-	-	-	990	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 990ms.
16:25:20.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:25:30.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:25:31.98	USH	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 990ms to 750ms.
16:25:37.62	USH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
16:25:41.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:25:48.48	SWS	-	-	-	250	NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 250ms.
16:25:49.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:25:52.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:25:55.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:25:57.41	LSH	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 990ms to 500ms.
16:26:03.05	LSH	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
16:26:06.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:26:11.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:26:26.13	USH	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
16:26:29.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
16:26:42.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:26:43.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:26:43.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:26:45.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
16:26:48.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:26:48.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:27:04.05	SWS	-	-	-	150	NIR int.time changed from 250ms to 150ms.
16:27:07.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:27:10.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:27:12.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:27:13.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:30:17.46	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 15ms to 50ms.
16:30:20.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:30:22.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:30:29.83	SWS	-	-	15	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 15ms.
16:30:32.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:30:34.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:32:39.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:32:39.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

16:32:39.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:32:41.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:32:44.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:32:44.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:36:08.37	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 15ms to 75ms.
16:36:11.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:36:13.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:38:04.16	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 50ms.
16:38:06.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:38:08.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:38:15.73	LSH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 100ms.
16:38:21.28	LSH	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
16:38:23.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:38:31.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:40:18.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:40:18.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:40:18.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:40:20.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:40:23.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:40:26.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:41:42.88	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
16:41:47.75	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 300ms.
16:41:51.94	SWS	-	-	-	350	NIR int.time changed from 150ms to 350ms.
16:41:55.69	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 750ms.
16:42:00.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:42:00.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:42:00.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:42:06.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:42:08.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:42:08.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:42:52.05	LSH	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 350ms.
16:42:58.26	LSH	-	-	-	990	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 990ms.
16:43:07.07	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
16:43:15.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:43:15.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:43:16.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:43:20.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:43:23.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:43:26.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:44:30.54	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run 1.2
16:44:32.66	SWS	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
16:44:39.08	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 300ms.
16:44:43.53	SWS	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
16:44:48.79	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
16:44:53.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:44:53.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:44:53.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:44:58.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:44:59.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:45:04.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:50:11.30	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 75ms.
16:50:16.28	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 200ms.
16:50:18.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:50:18.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:50:18.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:50:21.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:50:24.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:50:29.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:57:23.29	LSH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 300ms.
16:57:33.35	LSH	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
16:57:37.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:57:37.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:57:37.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:57:40.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:57:43.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:57:47.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:59:13.56	LSH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 200ms.
16:59:17.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:59:27.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

17:07:48.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:07:48.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:07:49.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:07:51.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:07:54.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:07:59.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:10:23.90	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 200ms.
17:10:30.83	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 400ms.
17:10:37.29	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
17:10:38.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:10:38.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:10:38.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:10:41.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:10:44.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:10:48.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:12:00.24	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of profile descent
17:14:36.04	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 2.1 171413
17:14:43.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:14:43.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:14:43.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:14:45.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:14:48.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:14:53.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:14:55.97	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 250ms.
17:15:00.46	SWS	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 300ms.
17:15:05.13	LSH	-	-	990	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 990ms.
17:15:12.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:15:14.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:15:18.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:15:22.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:16:23.72	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 990ms to 750ms.
17:16:26.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:16:37.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:18:28.93	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
17:18:31.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:18:42.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:21:17.30	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
17:21:23.78	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 100ms.
17:21:28.82	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
17:21:31.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:21:35.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:21:42.67	USH	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
17:21:46.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:21:46.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:21:46.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:21:50.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:21:50.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:21:57.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:21:59.16	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 50ms.
17:22:01.84	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
17:22:03.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:22:06.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:22:16.18	SWS	-	-	15	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 15ms.
17:22:20.93	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
17:22:23.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:22:25.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:22:30.90	USH	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
17:22:33.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:22:37.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:23:29.75	USH	-	-	-	350	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 350ms.
17:23:31.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:23:35.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:24:57.96	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
17:25:04.11	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 15ms to 300ms.
17:25:08.07	SWS	-	-	-	350	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 350ms.
17:25:11.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:25:12.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:25:12.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:25:16.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

17:25:16.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:25:22.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:26:36.98	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
17:26:42.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:26:53.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:26:59.82	USH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 200ms.
17:27:03.20	USH	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
17:27:07.86	USH	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 500ms.
17:27:12.20	USH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
17:27:17.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:27:23.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:28:50.70	USH	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
17:28:53.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:28:57.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:29:44.36	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
17:29:48.81	LSH	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 990ms to 750ms.
17:29:53.42	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
17:29:59.13	SWS	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 300ms.
17:30:06.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:30:06.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:30:07.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:30:10.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:30:11.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:30:15.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:36:12.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:36:12.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:36:12.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:36:15.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:36:17.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:36:20.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:36:57.40	SWS	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 350ms.
17:37:00.38	SWS	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 400ms.
17:37:03.18	SWS	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 500ms.
17:37:10.38	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
17:37:13.06	LSH	-	-	-	990	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 990ms.
17:37:15.96	USH	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
17:37:19.26	USH	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 250ms.
17:37:24.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:37:24.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:37:24.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:37:29.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:37:32.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:37:34.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:38:10.34	SWS	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
17:38:13.50	SWS	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 500ms.
17:38:20.01	LSH	-	-	990	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 990ms.
17:38:22.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:38:24.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:38:32.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:38:32.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:40:14.26	USH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 500ms.
17:40:19.56	USH	-	-	-	990	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 990ms.
17:40:23.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:40:28.50	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
17:40:31.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:40:33.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:40:39.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:41:33.13	USH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
17:41:36.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:41:47.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:41:57.06	USH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
17:42:00.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:42:11.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:42:54.27	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run 174240
17:51:27.38	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 5 at 3000ft 175107
17:52:34.19	USH	-	-	990	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 990ms.
17:52:35.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:52:36.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:52:36.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

17:52:44.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:52:46.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:52:46.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:53:47.83	USH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 990ms to 750ms.
17:53:54.35	USH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
17:53:59.83	USH	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 350ms.
17:54:04.62	USH	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 250ms.
17:54:15.07	USH	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 150ms.
17:54:19.35	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 400ms.
17:54:24.58	SWS	-	-	-	350	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 350ms.
17:54:29.71	USH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
17:54:37.28	USH	-	-	-	350	NIR int.time changed from 990ms to 350ms.
17:54:41.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:54:41.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:54:41.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:54:45.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:54:45.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:54:51.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:56:31.81	USH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 300ms.
17:56:36.73	USH	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 750ms.
17:56:43.56	SWS	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
17:56:49.02	SWS	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 500ms.
17:56:54.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:56:55.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:56:55.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:57:03.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:57:03.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:57:05.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:00:52.60	USH	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 150ms.
18:00:59.76	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 990ms to 750ms.
18:01:02.95	USH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
18:01:09.46	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 100ms.
18:01:14.04	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 250ms.
18:01:17.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:01:17.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:01:17.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:01:22.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:01:25.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:01:28.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:03:43.12	USH	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
18:03:48.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:03:53.62	SWS	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 300ms.
18:03:53.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:03:57.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:04:00.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:04:02.15	USH	-	-	-	350	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 350ms.
18:04:07.02	USH	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
18:04:09.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:04:12.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:06:21.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:06:21.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:06:22.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:06:25.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:06:25.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:06:32.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:07:44.31	LSH	-	-	990	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 990ms.
18:07:47.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:07:51.45	USH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 400ms.
18:07:55.19	USH	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 350ms.
18:07:57.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:07:59.82	USH	-	-	-	990	NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 990ms.
18:08:06.78	USH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 300ms.
18:08:15.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:08:26.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:08:55.63	USH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 100ms.
18:09:03.67	USH	-	-	-	350	NIR int.time changed from 990ms to 350ms.
18:09:09.17	USH	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
18:09:13.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:09:17.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

18:09:19.05	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 990ms to 750ms.
18:09:21.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:09:31.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:10:04.96	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
18:10:07.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:10:17.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:10:29.72	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
18:10:37.04	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 150ms.
18:10:42.26	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 50ms.
18:10:47.67	SWS	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 500ms.
18:10:52.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:10:52.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:10:52.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:10:56.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:10:58.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:11:02.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:11:21.93	SWS	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 300ms.
18:11:29.48	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
18:12:40.82	---	-	-	-	-	*** in run at 3000ft
18:13:10.29	SWS	-	-	15	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 15ms.
18:13:14.61	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
18:13:39.00	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
18:13:45.89	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 15ms to 300ms.
18:13:51.58	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
18:13:54.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:13:54.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:13:54.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:13:57.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:13:58.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:14:04.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:14:44.56	---	-	-	-	-	*** using improvised methods to maintain 174aft
18:17:47.64	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws head at 175 aft
18:18:29.55	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
18:33:06.21	SWS	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 350ms.
18:33:09.45	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 100ms.
18:33:15.36	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
18:33:17.97	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
18:33:25.45	LSH	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 150ms.
18:33:31.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:33:31.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:33:32.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:33:33.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:33:36.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:33:42.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:41:35.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:41:35.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:41:35.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:41:36.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:41:39.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:41:42.59	SWS	-	-	15	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 15ms.
18:41:46.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:44:41.62	LSH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
18:44:44.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:44:44.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:44:44.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:44:46.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:44:48.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:44:55.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:53:17.54	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 7 185258
18:53:27.23	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 15ms to 250ms.
18:53:32.26	SWS	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 300ms.
18:53:37.85	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 400ms.
18:53:44.90	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
18:53:49.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:53:49.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:53:49.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:53:53.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:53:53.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

18:53:59.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:54:26.86	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
18:54:30.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:54:41.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:58:40.49	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
18:58:46.14	LSH	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 350ms.
18:58:50.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:58:51.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:58:51.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:58:54.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:58:55.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:59:01.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:59:03.51	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 150ms.
18:59:08.03	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 75ms.
18:59:22.31	SWS	-	-	-	250	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
18:59:24.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:59:27.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:59:31.74	LSH	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 250ms.
18:59:36.05	LSH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 200ms.
18:59:39.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:59:43.42	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 50ms.
18:59:46.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:59:49.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:59:49.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:00:46.05	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
19:00:52.01	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 300ms.
19:00:56.35	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
19:00:59.41	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 250ms to 750ms.
19:01:03.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:01:03.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:01:04.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:01:07.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:01:11.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:01:14.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:01:33.58	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 200ms.
19:01:35.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:01:43.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:02:52.60	LSH	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 250ms.
19:02:57.23	LSH	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 350ms.
19:03:01.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:03:11.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:03:47.56	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
19:04:00.35	SWS	-	-	-	350	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 350ms.
19:04:05.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:04:05.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:04:06.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:04:09.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:04:10.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:04:16.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:04:19.61	LSH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 300ms.
19:04:22.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:04:32.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:04:33.82	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 75ms.
19:04:36.61	SWS	-	-	-	250	NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 250ms.
19:04:39.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:04:42.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:04:49.91	LSH	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
19:04:52.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:04:57.20	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 150ms.
19:05:02.54	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 200ms.
19:05:03.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:05:03.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:05:06.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:05:22.30	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 50ms.
19:05:27.13	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
19:08:19.90	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 250ms.
19:08:24.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:08:27.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:11:57.00	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 8

19:12:07.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:12:07.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:12:07.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:12:10.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:12:11.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:12:18.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:12:33.14	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 200ms.
19:13:01.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:13:04.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:13:09.97	LSH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 300ms.
19:13:13.75	LSH	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 350ms.
19:13:17.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:13:27.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:13:29.71	SWS	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 250ms to 300ms.
19:13:33.13	SWS	-	-	-	350	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 350ms.
19:13:42.60	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 300ms.
19:13:51.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:13:51.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:13:52.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:13:55.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:13:56.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:14:02.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:14:09.01	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
19:14:11.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:14:15.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:14:27.94	LSH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 300ms.
19:14:31.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:14:41.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:14:43.53	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 100ms.
19:14:49.15	SWS	-	-	-	150	NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 150ms.
19:14:51.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:14:53.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:14:54.54	LSH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
19:14:57.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:15:07.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:15:23.61	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
19:15:28.63	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 50ms.
19:15:31.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:15:33.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:15:34.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:16:13.55	USH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 100ms.
19:16:17.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:16:21.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:19:00.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:19:00.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:19:01.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:19:02.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:19:04.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:19:11.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:22:48.58	SWS	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 350ms.
19:22:54.48	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
19:22:58.92	SWS	-	-	-	250	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 250ms.
19:23:04.79	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 300ms.
19:23:07.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:23:11.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:23:12.17	LSH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 300ms.
19:23:18.54	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 400ms.
19:23:22.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:23:22.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:23:22.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:23:25.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:23:26.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:23:32.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:24:55.87	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
19:25:00.86	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 250ms to 750ms.
19:25:05.21	SWS	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 350ms.
19:25:09.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:25:09.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:25:09.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

19:25:13.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:25:17.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:25:19.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:27:33.11	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
19:27:38.77	SWS	-	-	-	350	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 350ms.
19:27:44.48	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 300ms.
19:27:50.98	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 500ms.
19:27:55.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:27:55.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:27:55.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:27:59.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:27:59.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:28:05.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:29:20.99	SWS	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 400ms.
19:29:33.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:29:38.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:29:38.65	USH	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 400ms.
19:29:40.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:29:44.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:29:58.73	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
19:30:02.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:30:13.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:30:42.11	LSH	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 350ms.
19:30:52.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:31:02.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:31:07.45	LSH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 300ms.
19:31:17.60	LSH	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
19:31:34.48	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
19:31:43.40	LSH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 200ms.
19:31:46.83	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
19:31:49.35	SWS	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 300ms.
19:31:54.15	LSH	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
19:32:00.17	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 75ms.
19:32:10.40	LSH	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 990ms to 750ms.
19:32:15.32	LSH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
19:32:17.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:32:18.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:32:18.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:32:21.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:32:22.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:32:26.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:32:33.69	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 50ms.
19:32:37.81	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
19:32:43.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:32:45.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:32:50.56	SWS	-	-	15	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 15ms.
19:32:54.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:32:57.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:33:01.53	LSH	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
19:33:04.98	LSH	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
19:33:10.10	SWS	-	-	-	150	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
19:33:16.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:33:16.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:33:16.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:33:17.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:33:20.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:33:21.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:35:04.41	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
19:35:10.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:35:11.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:36:31.02	SWS	-	-	-	150	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 150ms.
19:36:33.87	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 15ms to 50ms.
19:36:38.12	SWS	-	-	15	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 15ms.
19:36:43.31	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 15ms to 50ms.
19:36:46.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:36:48.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:37:43.23	SWS	-	-	15	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 15ms.
19:38:32.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:38:32.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

19:38:32.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:38:32.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:38:34.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
19:38:36.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:38:38.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:39:05.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:41:30.77	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 15ms to 150ms.
19:41:37.46	SWS	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 150ms to 300ms.
19:41:39.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:41:42.47	LSH	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 350ms.
19:41:42.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:41:48.24	LSH	-	-	-	990	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 990ms.
19:41:53.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:41:59.72	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 200ms.
19:42:01.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:42:03.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:42:04.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:43:29.59	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
19:43:53.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:43:53.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:43:53.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:43:57.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:43:57.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:44:04.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:46:03.84	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 75ms.
19:46:08.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:46:11.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:46:11.92	LSH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 300ms.
19:46:14.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:46:24.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:49:39.52	LSH	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
19:49:45.27	LSH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 200ms.
19:49:50.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:50:00.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:51:17.18	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
19:51:22.82	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 300ms.
19:51:26.26	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 400ms.
19:51:29.76	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 750ms.
19:51:34.13	SWS	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 500ms.
19:51:38.37	LSH	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
19:51:42.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:51:42.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:51:42.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:51:47.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:51:50.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:51:52.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:52:57.58	LSH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 200ms.
19:53:02.46	LSH	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 250ms.
19:53:05.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:53:15.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:53:55.21	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
19:53:59.10	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 200ms.
19:54:01.49	SWS	-	-	-	350	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 350ms.
19:54:06.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:54:07.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:54:07.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:54:11.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:54:11.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:54:18.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:54:47.93	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
19:54:52.85	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
19:54:57.37	SWS	-	-	-	250	NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 250ms.
19:55:01.22	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 75ms.
19:55:04.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:55:07.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:55:38.51	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 100ms.
19:55:43.83	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 250ms.
19:55:45.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:55:48.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

19:58:21.21	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of science for SWS
19:58:37.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
19:58:39.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
19:58:41.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
19:58:51.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
19:58:54.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
19:58:55.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
19:59:17.72	---	-	-	-	-	*** end

65535

ARIES flight log		Flight: <u>B287</u>	page <u>1</u> of <u> </u>
Date: <u>27/04/07</u>	Operator(s): <u>Joss</u>	Res: <u>1</u>	Gain A: <u>Z B2</u>
Loc./Notes: <u>1st Houston — over R ARM SITE @ OKLAHOMA</u>			

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
142611	GRD	Starm	ASC II				housekeeping.
150703		Monitored recording	ASC II				housekeeping
151258	Transit	1/60	Cal	clsd	7071	3174	FL181 calibration.
152229	Transit	1/60	Cal	clsd	7062	3091	CAL
152430	R1	1/60	CAL	clsd	7041	3049	
152550	R1	600/1	NW	clsd	707	3065	some cloud below
153054	R1	1/60	NW	clsd	7052	3091	
153201	R1	600/1	NW	clsd	7073	3082	
153320	R1	300/1	NW	clsd	7061	3085	short Rtd — didn't stop properly.
153620	R1	300/1	Zen	open	7030	3066	2. SW on Zen — cirrus above
153904	R1	1/60	Cal	clsd	7084	3071	
154020	R1	300/1	NW	clsd	7091	3064	
154307	R1	300/1	Zen	open	7026	3099	
154550	R1	1/60	Cal	clsd	7083	3071	
154724	R1	600/1	NW	clsd	7071	3015.	
155224	R1.1	1/60	Cal	clsd	7060	3058	
155409	R1.1	300/1	Zen	open	3071	70.54	
155646	R1.1	300/1	NW	clsd	7071	3072	
155929	R1.1	1/60	Cal	clsd	7086	3052.	
160056	R1-2	600/1	NW	clsd	7043	3074	
160614	R1-2	1/60	Cal	clsd	7061	3070	
160730	R1-2	600/1	NW	clsd	7062	3058	
161235	R1-2	1/60	Cal	clsd	7059	3054	
161359	R1-2	300/1	Zen	open			
161654	R1-2	300/1	NW	clsd	7071	3073	
161929	R1-2	1/60	Cal	clsd	7076	3085	
162047	R1-2	600/1	NW	clsd	7075	3074	
162550	R1-2	1/60	Cal	clsd	7081	3087	
162716	R1-2	600/1	NW	clsd	7129	3079.	
163310	R1-2	1/60	Cal	clsd	7123	3061	
163453	R1-2	600/1	NW	clsd	7066	3103	

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ARIES flight log

Flight: B 287

page 2 of

Date: 27/04/06

Operator(s): Joss

Res: 1

Gain A: 2B2

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
161040	R1.2	1/60	Cal	Clsd	7062	3061	
161224	R1.2	300/1	Zen	Open	6981	3078	
161411	R1.2	300/1	Nod	Clsd	7045	3019	
171401	R2.1	1/60	Cal	Clsd	7063	3080	
171527	R2.1	600/1	Nod	Clsd	7088	3085	
172038	R2.1	1/60	Cal	Clsd	7071	3073	
172156	R2.1	300/1	Zen	Open	7041	3118	Some cloud above
172433	R2.1	300/1	Nod	Clsd	7088	3065	
172714	R2.1	1/60	Cal	Clsd	7065	3075	
172850	R2.1	600/1	Nod	Clsd	7088	3070	
173419	R2.1	1/60	Cal	Clsd	7083	3082	
173542	R2.1	600/1	Nod	Clsd	7088	3091	
174160	R2.1	1/60	Cal	Clsd	7090	3106	
174350	R2.2	1/60	Cal	Clsd	7071	3076	3700'
174929	R2.2	600/1	Nod	Clsd	7088	3099	Over OIA/KONA CITY. end 174723
174723							
174723	R2.3	300/1	Nod	Clsd	7076	3096	end 174944
175042	R5	1/60	Cal	Clsd	7088	3084	3000'
175203	R5	600/1	Nod	Clsd	7072	3096	2800'
175738	R5	1/60	Cal	Clsd	7072	3096	
175856	R5	600/1	Nod	Clsd	7079	3085	
180402	R5	1/60	Cal	Clsd	7079	3096	
180626	R5	600/1	Nod	Clsd	7085	3068	180952 finish
181020	R5	300/1	Zen	Open	7042	3080	3000' from finish 181242
181258	R6	1/60	Cal	Clsd	7111	3177	
181417	R6	400/1	Nod	Clsd	7109	3128	
181749	R6	1/60	Cal	Clsd	7090	3116	
185310	R7	600/1	Cal	Clsd	7093	3071	
185427	R7	600/1	Nod	Clsd	7062	3087	
185928	R7	1/60	Cal	Clsd	7071	3078	
190000	R7	300/1	Zen	Open	7015	3092	

ARIES flight log

Flight:

13287

page 5 of

Date: 27/04/07

Operator(s): Joss

Res: ↑

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Fit ptrn	Scans	View	Sht	HBB	CBB	Comments
190302	R7	1/60	cal	clsd			
190322	R7	300/1	Nwd	clsd	70.98	30.78	end 190525
190536	R7	1/60	cal	clsd	70.42	30.61	
190938	R7	1/60	cal	clsd	70.32	30.66	
191146	R8	600/1	Nwd	clsd	70.64	30.56	
191649	R8	1/60	cal	clsd	70.63	30.52	
191806	R8	600/1	Nwd	clsd	70.62	30.02	
192307	R9	1/60	cal	clsd	70.52	30.21	
192430	R8	300/1	Zen	open			
192708	R8	300/1	Nwd	clsd	70.65	30.02	
192838	R8	1/60	cal	clsd	70.2	30.02	
193055	R8	600/1	Nwd	clsd	70.76	30.70	
193633	R8	1/60	cal	clsd	70.86	30.58	
193747	R8	600/1	Nwd	clsd	70.61	30.56	- fuelled @ 8km
193952							
194050	R8	300/1	Nwd	clsd	70.64	30.87	
194313	R8	1/60	cal	clsd	70.64	30.77	
194433	R8	600/1	Nwd	clsd	70.76	30.40	
194435	R8	1/60	cal	clsd			
195055	R8	300/1	Zen	open	69.74	30.55	
195532	R8	300/1	Nwd	clsd	70.22	30.73	
195627	R8	1/60	cal	clsd	70.61	30.62	

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	27/04/06	Flight	B287	log pages	2
Operator(s)	Pollard		Campaign	JAIVEX			
Departure	Houston		Arrival	Houston			

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection							X	
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers							X	
Close all MARSS circuit breakers							X	
FERA on	at time						12:39:39	
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	20	Ch	19.9	Ch18	19.4		
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C		
MARSS CPU on	at time						12:44:18	
Initial target temperatures	Hot	290.9	Cold	290.3				
Target heating							X	
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***							X	
Scanning on (LMD box)	at time						12:45:53	
Scan indication	Monitor >			Visual				X

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers								
Turn on Deimos CPU								
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***								
Start Deimos Software	at time							
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold					
Target heating								
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual				
Weather	Cloud				Precip			
	Surface				Pressure			
	Other							

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	Set	at time		13:28:55		
Brightness temps 'sensible'							X
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	345	Cold	292		
	Deimos:	Hot		Cold			
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B			
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)			
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20		
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)		
	1	33.14	37.86	39.86	41.66		

Power changeover

Headset on before start							
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.						
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)							
Exit Deimos Software (x)							
POWER CHANGEOVER							
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton						
Restart Deimos Software							
System running again	at time						

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B.287**.....

 Date 27/04/2007.....

 Operator's name: D. TLODEMAN.....

 Page 1 of 2.....

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
1508	climb	↗	12	5	30	21°	22°	Cooling water for high level
1525	Run 1	26 kft	12.7	0.0	14.9	OFF	5°	Tuned off for high level (chiller)
1533								Stopped Labview to do dry neph and zero
153803								Labview back on
1646	Probe 1	28 kft	13.7	6.0	19.4	25°	16°	Chiller on
1710	Probe 1	32 kft	13.5	39.9	30.8	23°	5°	
1714	Run 2-1	2700 ft	13.5	43.5	39.5	23°	13°	
1717	"	2700 ft	13.5	44.5	61.0	30°	30°	Humidity out 86%
1719	"	"	13.5	44.9	61.8	23°	30°	
1722	"	"	13.5	42.8	66.8	25°	32°	
1725	"	"	13.6	49.4	72.8	25°	35°	
1735	"	"	13.6	50.4	48.6	25°	15°	No growth seen yet
1745	Run 3	3700 ft	13.2	50.4	80.2	24°	35°	
1747	Run 4	4000 ft	13.1	54.5	96.2	-	40°	
1748						25°		
1756	Run 5	2800 ft	13.7	53.3	54.6	24°	16°	
1801	"	"	13.4	61.5	96.9	25°	40°	
1811	"	3000 ft	13.5	57.5	56.8	24°	17°	A little growth seen
1816	Run 6		13.6	57.5	88.5	25°	40°	

1447 27216/1044/26400/1015
1514 33768/1296/32880/1260
BL ~ 3500ft

200 Indicated
338 True
313

TWC failed on take off - status light is flashing as soon as switch on

* Doug - chemistry logs when problems? *

1068 - 2
3008 3
5021 - 4
7391 - 5

1553 43344/1656/42240/1645

Optical disk did not have a name - reloaded new & got a satcom message from Exeter - may have been a coincidence.

1735 67788/2592/4800/210

Nez vane broken not picking up all of the time but 1q water picked up storm
Took a while for TWC to recover but measuring @ 1739.

⇒ change flight summary.

Unsure if emails coming of a/c

Possibly sampled Oklahoma plume as flew N → S & wind 180 degree.

Point D chemical BL ~ 5000ft.

SEADAS computer crashed @ 1841

1906 89712/3420/18240/700
1937 97020/3708/25680/980

Sonde 8.

1909 Up & running

SID 2 dead 1926 onwards.

Stratospheric air seen ~1939 - 262ppbV@1942

back 1955

1545L 1615L
2045 2115Z.

Stu inform WB |

Flight:

B287

KEY

- Duff Data
- Minor Problems
- OK
- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nezvorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

Report Created 26/06/2007
15:35:52

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turb Centre-Static:
- Turb Left Right:
- Turb Up-Down:
- Turb Horizontal Chk:
- Turb Vertical Chk:
- Weather Radar:
- DLUs:**
- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

- Lower:**
- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:
- Upper:**
- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:
- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Last Updated:

27/04/2007

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:
- Aerosol**
- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3025 (AMS):
- INC:
- VACC:
- CPC 3010A (CVI):

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:
- Misc Non-Core**
- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B287

Date: 27 April 2007

Instruments

1. TWC breaker not pushed in until end of run 1
2. Do not seem to be receiving satcom messages

Aircraft

Nil

Satcom-H Calls

Nil

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 27/04/07
[Signature]

Flight No: B287

Pre-Flighter: JT

<u>Item</u>	<u>√ or x</u>	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
1	<input type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	N/A.
<u>Aircraft Cabin</u>				
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nezvorov	Checked and OFF	
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GPS	Checked	
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Align	
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	- DATA ON NOX LOOK V. ↑
16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
17	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	FWVS	Set up	JOSS KEANT
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC	ON & Checked	NOT FILTER AS YET
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked	
23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Navigate then back to Align	
24	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hubs x 4	Checked ON	
25	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	& CB on Port Fwd SSP
26	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	
27	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	Set up	
28	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			

External Checks overleaf →

Pre-Flighter's Log

<u>Item</u> \checkmark or \times	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
<u>External</u>			
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	BW
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> GE	Cleaned & Checked	SLIPPING
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Camera Windows	Cleaned	FULL OF WATER AGAIN ! CHANGED -
37	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TWC Cover	Fitted if required	NOT FITTED YET
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> All other covers	Removed	
40	<input type="checkbox"/> Dustbin	Returned to hangar	N/A
41	<input type="checkbox"/> Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	<input type="checkbox"/> Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>			<u>Signed</u>
43	<input type="checkbox"/> Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		
44	<input type="checkbox"/> ICEX applied		
45	<input type="checkbox"/> Traps empty (weekly only)		

H631 ON
H490 OFF

Flight Manager's Data Processing Status

Flight No: B287
Flight Manger: RMP

Date of flight: 27 -04-07

Mfd data must be backed up within a week.

If it can't be done by the Cloud Physics Operator in that time the **FM must back it up**

<u>On day of flight</u>		
Action	Link / Option	Date
Update Database & Note BBR Fit	Database	27.4.07
Create Fltcons & check BBR fit	Option 9	28.4.07
Transfer & process Data	Option 2	28.04.07
Ftp qldata to BADC	project_spaces/faam/quicklook	N/A
Check Rawdata	flight_plot	28.04.07
Raw data to BADC	Option 7	28.07.04
Copy & Convert Fltsumm file	Copy from optical to fltsumm directory Set def fltsumm run tarexec:convert_summ	28.04.07
Edit Fltsumm/ send to BADC	Option 10	
Copy Flight logs	Flight Logs	28.04.07
Download photos, clear camera & email Doug	To Flight Logs and Turb Probe Photos	N/A
Ftp CGPS.bin file to BADC	project_spaces/faam/javad_gps	
Check Mfddata	flight_plot	28.04.07

<u>On day after flight</u>		
Action	Link / Option	Date
Ftp PSAP to FLOODS	Bnnn_psap_data	28.04.07
Merge PSAP into mfddata	wave .run mergepsap bnnn_mfda (b,c)	28.04.07
Record mfd changes	edit mfddata:mfddata.txt	28.04.07
NETCDF to BADC	Option 4	28.04.07
Upload .nc from BADC	To USB stick (WS_FTP Pro)	28.04.07
Data quality check	Run Checkg on Linux pc	28.04.07
Ftp file to BADC	core_faam_yyyymm dd_r0_bnnn_quality.txt	28.04.07
Print out quality file	put in Faults Book	
Backup raw data to optical	Option 6	28.07.04
Backup mfd if Cloud Physics Operator can't	MFD Backup Instructions.doc	
Ftp mfd to BADC	Not yet set up	Watch this space
Video tapes to cupboard	Video Tape Log	28.04.07
Complete & save this form	Data Processing Logs	

Flight B287 18:17:06

Heading 178 deg Speed 233 knots Height 2.8kft Press 911mb

Lat 33°30.0'N Long 97°30.0'W Wind 4 ms-1/ 189 deg

Temp 15.8C Dewpoint 9.72C

From 15:00:25 to now

Current values
INU LONGITUDE -97.59 deg (+ve E)
INU LATITUDE 33.59 deg (+ve N)

Flight B287 18:35:29

Heading 352 deg Speed 292 knots Height 16.8kft Press 530mb

Lat 34°30.0'N Long 97°30.0'W Wind 21 ms-1/ 274 deg

Temp -13.61C Dewpoint -13.26C

From 18:15 to now

	Current values		
	PRESSURE HEIGHT	16.87	Kft
++++	TECO NO	0.74	ppb
++++	TECO NO2	-0.14	ppb
++++	TECO NOx	0.49	ppb

New plot, same times

Flight B287 18:18:43

Heading 196 deg Speed 227 knots Height 2.8kft Press 911mb

Lat 33°24.0'N Long 97°30.0'W Wind 5 ms-1/ 252 deg

Temp 15.75C Dewpoint 10.35C

From 16:45 to now

Current values				
—	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	65922	secs	<input checked="" type="radio"/> All
—	TECO NO	2.4	ppb	<input type="radio"/>
—	TECO NO2	6.21	ppb	<input type="radio"/>
—	TECO NOx	8.48	ppb	<input type="radio"/>

Flight B287 15:21:47

Heading 321 deg Speed 349 knots Height 26.0kft Press 359mb

Lat 30°48.0'N Long 95°42.0'W Wind 34 ms-1/ 267 deg

Temp -28.89C Dewpoint -28.66C

From 15:00:25 to now

	Current values		
	PRESSURE HEIGHT	26.05	Kft
++++	OZONE MIXING RATIO	44.11	ppb
++++	CO MIXING RATIO	138.49	ppb
			⊙ All
			⊙
			⊙

Profile out of Houston

Flight B287 17:13:14

Heading 183 deg Speed 208 knots Height 2.5kft Press 922mb

Lat 37°18.0'N Long 97°30.0'W Wind 15 ms-1/ 287 deg

Temp 13.98C Dewpoint 7.38C

From 16:45 to now

	Current values		
	PRESSURE HEIGHT	2.58	Kft
++++	OZONE MIXING RATIO	52.95	ppb
++++	CO MIXING RATIO	500.72	ppb
			⊂ All
			⊙
			⊃

New plot, same times

Flight B287 18:18:36

Heading 182 deg Speed 231 knots Height 2.8kft Press 911mb

Lat 33°24.0'N Long 97°30.0'W Wind 7 ms-1/ 226 deg

Temp 15.77C Dewpoint 10.51C

From 14:13:15 to now

Current values			
— TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	65916	secs	Ⓞ All
— OZONE MIXING RATIO	57.32	ppb	Ⓞ
— CO MIXING RATIO	236.56	ppb	Ⓞ

New plot, same times

Flight B287 19:58:08

Heading 172 deg Speed 346 knots Height 31.0kft Press 287mb

Lat 33°12.0'N Long 96°54.0'W Wind 50 ms-1/ 258 deg

Temp -43.19C Dewpoint -54.48C

From 14:13:15 to now

Current values				
—	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	71886	secs	<input checked="" type="radio"/> All
—	OZONE MIXING RATIO	77.74	ppb	<input type="radio"/>
—	CO MIXING RATIO	162.34	ppb	<input type="radio"/>

Flight B287 15:21:06

Heading 321 deg Speed 348 knots Height 25.7kft Press 364mb

Lat 30°42.0'N Long 95°42.0'W Wind 33 ms-1/ 265 deg

Temp -27.72C Dewpoint -28.92C

From 15:00:25 to now

	Current values		
	STATIC PRESSURE	364.64	mb
++++	DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	-27.73	deg C
++++	DEW POINT	-28.92	deg C

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B287:

Log	Reason
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
FWVS	No log is taken for this FWVS
AMS	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	31 Aug 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Upward Facing Cameras
3 x Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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